

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINIUM HONEYCOMB SANDWICHES

E. Kara^{1*}, V. Crupi², G. Epasto², E. Guglielmino², H. Aykul¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Hitit University, Çorum, Turkey, ² Department of Electronic Engineering, Chemistry and Industrial Engineering, University of Messina, Messina, Italy

*Corresponding author (emrekara@hitit.edu.tr)

Keywords: *Aluminum honeycomb sandwich, Low velocity impact, Computed Tomography, IR Thermography, Light-weight structures, Transport applications*

1 Introduction

The sandwich structures with aluminium core are suitable for lightweight transportation systems, such as for bus [1] and ship [2, 3] structures. The weight minimization influences the energy efficiency of the transport vehicles; by saving weight, fuel efficiency and load carrying capacity increase. Altenbach presented a review of the mechanics of advanced composite materials for lightweight structures in [4]. Petras and Sutcliffe [5] investigated sandwich beam, made of glass fiber reinforced plastic (*GFRP*) laminate skins and Nomex honeycomb cores, in static three-point bending, obtaining the failure mode maps. Belingardi et al. [6] analysed the fatigue strength of sandwich beams with aluminium honeycomb core and composite face sheets through four-point bending tests, while Demelio et al. [7] investigated in the static and fatigue behaviour of sandwich panels with Nomex honeycomb and composite skins joined by fasteners. Impact behaviour of sandwich structures is dominated by the deformation of the core [8], which gets crushed as transverse stresses become large. Core deformation and failure are decisive factors for the energy absorption capability of sandwich structures. With aluminium honeycomb cores, damage consists of crushing or buckling of cell walls in a region surrounding the impact point. Hazizan et al. [9] conducted low-velocity impact tests in order to investigate the response of sandwiches, made of aluminium honeycomb core and glass fibre reinforced/epoxy skins. The low-velocity impact response of square sandwich plates, made of carbon/epoxy skins bonded to aluminium Nomex honeycomb was analyzed by Foo et al. [10]. An energy balance model was used in both the experimental investigations [9, 10], obtaining good

agreement between the model prediction and the experimental data. The structural response in the case of low-velocity impact on Nomex honeycomb sandwiches was predicted using a numerical approach, based on a grid of nonlinear springs, and a good correlation with experimental drop tests was achieved [11]. Zhu et al. [12] developed damage and failure mode maps for composite sandwich panels subject to quasi-static indentation and low velocity impact tests. Low velocity impact tests have been already conducted on glass fiber reinforced aluminium foam sandwich (*GFR-AFS*) panels by the authors [13]. The aim of this study was the analysis of the bending and low-velocity impact responses of glass fiber reinforced aluminium honeycomb sandwiches (*GFR-AHS*) and the comparison with the aluminium honeycomb sandwiches (*AHS*) without *GFRP* outer skins in terms of peak loads and absorbed energy. The static (bending and penetration tests) and dynamic (low velocity impact tests) behaviour of *AHS* panels was already analyzed by some of the authors [14]. The failure mode and the internal damage of the *GFR-AHS* panels have been investigated using two experimental techniques: 3D Computed Tomography (CT) [3, 13], that allows a three-dimensional reconstruction of the analysed object, and Infrared thermography (IRT), already used for analyzing the impact responses of aluminium and PVC foam sandwiches [15]. Meola and Carlomagno [16] investigated the behaviour of glass fibres reinforced polymer (GFRP) under low velocity impact by means of IRT. From the analysis of temperature maps it was possible to get information about damage threshold and extension. One main finding of their study regards a relationship between the damaged area and the effective striking surface.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The specimens were made bonding two *GFRP* skins to *AHS* panels using a commercial adhesive. Two different aluminium honeycomb sandwich typologies have been investigated: 1/8-5052-0.0020 and 1/4-5052-0.0025; the designation corresponds to cell size (inch) – alloy – foil thickness (inch). The physical and geometrical properties of the *GFR-AHS* panels are reported in Table 1. Hand lay-up method was used to produce the outer skins, made of glass fiber reinforced epoxy matrix, and the skins were bonded onto the aluminium faces of *AHS* panels using SikaFlex-265 commercial adhesive (Table 2). The adhesive thickness is about 1.5 mm.

2.2 Methods

The static bending tests were carried out on *GFR-AHS* specimens using a servo-hydraulic load machine, while low-velocity impact tests were performed by means of a drop test machine. After the first impact, the rebound brake is activated to avoid multiple impacts. The mass of the striker and the drop height are variable, allowing for a wide range of impact energies. The hemispherical steel tip of diameter of 20 mm is instrumented by means of strain gauge.

The failure mode and the internal damage of the impacted *GFR-AHS* have been investigated by a 3D CT system and an IR camera.

The CT system is equipped with a X-ray source having maximum voltage and current of 225 kV and 7.1 mA, respectively, depending on the focal spot size that can be chosen among these values: 250 μm , 300 μm , 500 μm and 800 μm . The detector system is a flat panel with a resolution of 1920 x 1536 pixels. The scans, reported in this paper, were conducted with 250 μm focal spot size and X-rays were set at a voltage of 150 kV and at a current of about 1.3 mA. A Cu filter was used to improve image contrast. It is worth noting that the source-detector and the source-sample distances are critical in determining the magnification of the sample and, thus, the resolution of the scan: the closer the sample was to the source and the further away from the detector, the higher the magnification. A conical X-ray beam scanned the sample, which was rotated at increments of 0.5°/s for each rotation step. This procedure was then repeated until a full rotation

of 360° was achieved and a total of 1440 projections were then obtained to be used in the 3D profile generation. The sizes of the voxels and images were 0.050 mm and 2048 x 2048 pixels respectively. The integration time was chosen equal to 250 ms.

During the impact tests, the thermal behaviour of the specimens was monitored by an IR camera (FLIR Systems SC 7200) equipped with a 320 x 256 pixels InSb focal plane array cooled detector working in the MWIR (1.5 - 5 μm) spectral band (NETD 20 mK typical). A 50 mm focal length lens (FOV 11° x 8.8°) was used. The camera was placed at about 500 mm in front of the specimen, focusing the side view of the specimen. The thermographic images were acquired at a frame rate of 472 Hz (2 ms) in sub array windowing (160 x 128 pixel) with Altair software. Since the impact event happens in a very short time, high frame rates are useful to catch fast temperature variations.

A theoretical approach [3, 14], based on the energy balance model, has been applied to investigate their impact behaviour. The model parameters were obtained from the measurements carried out on the *CT* images of the impacted panels and not from the results of static tests, as it is usually done in literature.

3 Results

3.1 Static Bending Tests

Static three-point bending tests were performed on *GFR-AHS* panels (150 x 50 x 18 mm) at different support span distances ($L = 55, 70, 80, 125$ mm), applying the load at a constant rate of 2 mm/min and with a preload of 10 N. The average values of the weight for the investigated panels are: 53.41 g for *AHS* panels ($d = 3$ mm) and 125.18 g for the same panels with *GFRP* skins, 51.09 g *AHS* panels ($d = 6$ mm) and 119.97 g for the same panels with *GFRP* skins.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the load deflection curves obtained under bending tests carried out at different values of support span on the two typologies of *GFR-AHS* (cell diameter $d = 3$ and 6 mm). The initial linear-elastic behaviour is followed by an elasto-plastic phase until a peak value is reached, after which there is an abrupt load loss, which is more evident respect to the behaviour of sandwich panels with similar skins, made of glass fiber reinforced epoxy matrix, and aluminium foam core [13]. This different behaviour is due to the honeycomb core shear. After the peak load

and the subsequent load loss, the behaviour differs for the honeycomb panels with different cell sizes: in the curves for the sandwiches with $d = 3$ mm the load increases smoothly, while for the panels with $d = 6$ mm load remains almost constant. The same trend was observed in the load- deflection curves for *AHS* panels without the outer skins, under three point bending tests at the same support span values [14]. The amount of the energy absorption E was evaluated integrating the load - deflection curves, obtained by the bending tests. The values of energy efficiency η were considered in order to compare the bending tests at different support spans L . The efficiency η is defined as the absorbed energy up to failure deflection δ_{max} normalized by the energy absorption of the ideal absorber [17]:

$$\eta = \frac{E}{E_i} = \frac{\int_0^{\delta_{max}} F d\delta}{F_{max} \cdot \delta_{max}} \quad (1)$$

where F_{max} is the highest force occurring during the bending test.

Assuming a perfect bond between the faces and the core and eliminating the possibility of delamination, sandwich beams can fail by several modes in bending tests: core shear, face yield, indentation and face wrinkling, this last mode occurs generally only for sandwich beams with corrugated or honeycomb core. The specimens after the bending tests are shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 shows the CT images along the middle section of the damaged *GFR-AHS* panels ($d = 3$ and 6 mm) after bending tests at different values of support spans ($L = 55, 70, 80$ and 125 mm). CT analyses show that the most frequent failure mode is indentation for the 2 typologies of sandwich. The observed collapse mode differs from the traditional mechanism of indentation, reported in literature [5], because it is accompanied by the rotation of the two halves of the sample around the mid-plane and by the formation of a plastic hinge also in the tensioned face. Core shear is also evident in the panel with $d = 3$ mm at a support span of 80 mm (Fig. 4).

The partial debonding of the glass fibre reinforced/epoxy skins occurs for all the panels with $d = 6$ mm (Figs. 3 and 4). It is probably due to the fact that the skins cannot follow the core deformation, that is obviously greater for the panels with $d = 6$ mm.

The average values of the bending results corresponding to the *GFR-AHS* sandwiches are reported in Table 3 and compared to the values obtained for *AHS* [14]. The experimental results confirm that the ability to absorb energy of the honeycomb sandwiches is obviously affected by the cell size and the presence of GFRP outer skins.

The best response in terms of energy efficiency, as reported in Table 3, was obtained for the *GFR-AHS* with $d = 3$ mm, subjected to bending loads with support span values $L = 55$ and 70 mm. It is due to the peak force value which was influenced by the cell size of the honeycomb and GFRP skins and hence the higher rigidity of the whole panel that was affected by the support span length.

3.2 Low-velocity Impact Tests

The low-velocity impact tests were performed on the two typologies of *GFR-AHS*. Dynamic impact tests were performed on specimens with a striker mass of 7.045 kg and different values of impact velocity ranging from 3 to 10 ms^{-1} . The impact energy values range from 32 to 352 J. The *GFR-AHS* specimens (75x50x17.5 mm) were fully clamped around their edges by a cylindrical support-ring with an inner diameter of 40 mm, without crushing the sample. The average values of the weight for the investigated panels are: 26.68 g for *AHS* panels ($d = 3$ mm) and 60.76 g for the same panels with GFRP skins, 25.32 g *AHS* panels ($d = 6$ mm) and 59.73 g for the same panels with GFRP skins.

The load – displacement curves at different impact velocities are given in Figs. 5 and 6 for *GFR-AHS*. The curves have the same stiffness for each of the two *GFR-AHS* typologies (cell diameter $d = 3$ and 6 mm) and a different number of load peaks. A typical load–displacement curve of a honeycomb sandwich [12] can be divided into two stages: the first stage is linear and the second one begins after the damage initiation. The failure is expected to occur by the collapse mechanism that produces the minimum limit load, but it could happen that after the initiation of a damage mode, other damage modes maybe triggered and the damage interaction and propagation are coupled in the second stage until the final failure. The area under this curve is approximately equal to the energy absorbed E during the impact, which is an important parameter to design a sandwich panel with good impact resistance. The load peak after the first stage is the critical

contact force for damage initiation F_c , which is not always the maximum load F_{max} because there is generally a second peak load F_{2P} at the end of the second stage before the failure. In the impact curves for AHS panels [14] the critical load has the maximum value and there is a lower peak load after the damage progression, whereas the presence of GFRP outer skins produces the maximum load at the end of the second stage as it results from the curves of Figs 5 and 6.

The energy amount, required to produce the complete failure of the sandwiches, was evaluated equal to: 128 J for AHS panels with $d = 3$ mm, 116 J for AHS panels with $d = 6$ mm and about 300 J for the same panels with GFRP skins. The experimental results confirm that, as expected, the GFR-AHS sandwiches are able to absorb greater amounts of energy respect to AHS panels. The results of the experimental tests in terms of absorbed energy and contact force peaks were compared with AHS panels [3] in Table 4.

The impact behaviour of the investigated sandwiches was confirmed in the post-impact inspection; the bottom and the lateral views of the panels after impact tests at different velocities are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. Fig. 9 shows the CT images along the middle section of the damaged GFR-AHS panels ($d = 3$ and 6 mm) after impact tests at different values of impact velocity ($v = 3 \div 9 \text{ ms}^{-1}$). The complete debonding of the glass fibre reinforced/epoxy skins occurs generally for panels with $d = 6$ mm (Figs. 7 – 10) as for the panels subjected to bending tests. The reason is due to the higher core displacement even at low impact velocities for the panels with higher cell size. Fig. 10 reports the stereomicroscope image (magnitude equal to 6.3 x) of a GFR-AHS panel ($d = 6$ mm) after impact test at $v = 7 \text{ m/s}$. It is clearly visible that the GFRP skin cannot follow this displacement of the panel, while the adhesion between the glue and the aluminium skin is perfect. The impact behaviour of the sandwiches with two cell sizes ($d = 3$ and 6 mm) confirms their bending response, where the debonding of GFRP skin occurs for panels with $d = 6$ mm.

The CT analyses of the GFR-AHS panels (Fig. 9) have shown that the collapse of the panel occurs for the initial deformation of the upper skin and for the buckling of the core cells. The analysis of the CT images (Fig. 9) of the panels with smaller cells ($d = 3$ mm) reveals that the collapse of the cells is located in the area concerned by the impact, while the rest of the structure remains almost intact. Instead, with the same

initial energy of impact, the collapse of the panels with larger cells ($d = 6$ mm) affects almost all cells. The same behaviour was detected for AHS panels subjected to impact loading [14]. The collapse of AHS [14] and GFR-AHS panels with honeycomb core occurred for the buckling of the cells and is strongly influenced by the cell size. Their capacity of absorbing energy depends on the mechanical properties of the composite skin and honeycomb core.

The temperature increment and the thermograms of the GFR-AHS panels ($d = 3$ and 6 mm) during the impact tests at $v = 7 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ are visible in Fig. 11. The image subtraction was applied in order to obtain more information and make easier the damage detection.

The ΔT plot, taken just before the impact, shows an overall uniform $\Delta T = 0$ distribution related to an unloaded condition. At the moment of the impact, the specimen experiences a cooling down ($0.07 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the 2 typologies) because of the thermo-elastic effect [16]; this cooling down lasts for fractions of a second. The cooling down is followed by abrupt heating up (thermoplastic effect) for the two typologies of specimens (Fig. 11). The different behaviour of the specimen can be explained considering that, as the temperature rises as the damage becomes more important: $35.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the specimen with $d = 3$ mm and $42.39 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the specimen with $d = 6$ mm. This assumption is confirmed also by the CT analyses (Fig. 9). After the temperature peak and its subsequent decrement, there is a different trend in the ΔT -t curves for the GFR-AHS panels with different cell sizes: for the sandwiches with $d = 6$ mm the temperature remains almost constant, while for the panels with $d = 3$ mm the temperature has a low increment until an almost asymptotic temperature is achieved. The obtained results confirm that the on-line monitoring of the impact using IRT is a useful tool for material characterization.

Zhou et al. [12] analyzed the failure modes of composite sandwich panels, made of Nomex honeycomb core with carbon fiber-epoxy composite skins, and obtained the failure mode map using the material parameters. The same failure mode map [12] was used for the investigated GFR-AHS panels and shown in Fig. 12. According to the geometric parameters (skin thickness t_s , core thickness t_c , impactor radius R_i) the failure mode predicted by the failure map is the core buckling and close to the matrix shear damage as confirmed by the experimental investigation.

3.3 Energy Balance Model

The impact response of the *GFR-AHS* panels with $d = 6$ mm was modelled using a theoretical approach, based on the energy-balance model. More information on the developed approach are reported in other papers of the authors [3, 14]. The obtained results were compared with those reported in [9].

The energy balance for the sandwich structure can be obtained considering that the initial kinetic energy is equal to the energy absorption in bending, shear and contact effects:

$$\frac{1}{2}mv^2 = E_b + E_s + E_c = \frac{1}{2K_{bs}}F_{\max}^2 + \frac{1}{(n+1)K_i^n}F_{\max}^{1+\frac{1}{n}} \quad (2)$$

where m and v are the mass and the impact velocity of the impactor, K_{bs} is the linear stiffness including bending and shear effects, K_i and n are material constants. The subscript b , s , m and c of eq. (2) refer to energy dissipation in bending, shear, membrane and contact effects, respectively

This theoretical approach has been applied in the current study to investigate the impact response of *GFR-AHS* sandwiches in order to compare the results with *AHS* panels [14]. This energy-balance model, once validated using data from tests carried out at some impact velocities, can be used to predict the maximum impact force for a given impact velocity or energy applying eq. (2).

The parameters of the energy balance model are generally determined in literature from the results of static tests. In this scientific research the parameters were obtained directly from the measurements carried out on the CT images (Fig. 13); the vertical displacement w_b of the core at bottom face sheet interface and the impactor displacement w_i were measured by analysing the CT images of midplanes of the panels subjected to impact loading, which didn't produce the complete failure of the panels. The core compression displacement α is obtained by the subtraction between the impactor displacement w_i and the vertical displacement w_b of the core.

According to the spring-mass model, it can be assumed a linear relationship between the impact load and the corresponding global displacement w_b of the sandwich panel and the K_{bs} stiffness is the slope of

this linear function, so the K_{bs} stiffness was assessed in the present research paper as shown in Fig. 14 by the slope of the linear function interpolating the peak loads F_{\max} , obtained by the impact tests at different impact velocities, versus the corresponding bending and shear deflections w_b of the midplane of the panel, that were measured using the CT.

The contribution of the energy dissipation due to bending and shear E_{bs} was evaluated applying eq. (2) and the contact energy E_c was obtained simply by subtracting these values of E_{bs} from the values of the total dissipated energy. Considering the bilogarithmic expression of the equation of the contact energy E_c , a linear equation is obtained:

$$\log(E_c) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)\log(F_{\max}) - \left[\log(n+1) + \frac{1}{n}\log(K_i)\right] \quad (3)$$

The values of the contact energy E_c were plotted versus the corresponding values of the peak load F_{\max} in a bilogarithmic scale and a linear regression was performed in order to assess the contact parameters (n , K_i), as shown in Fig. 15; the value of n was obtained by the slope of the linear equation interpolating the data and the value of K_i by the constant term of the linear equation.

The obtained values of the K_i and n constants are: $n = 0.64$ and $K_i = 1.85E5 \text{ Nm}^{-0.64}$ for *AHS* with cell size $d = 6$ mm and $n = 1.34$ and $K_i = 4.86E6 \text{ Nm}^{-1.34}$ for the same panels with GFRP skins. The values of the material parameters, predicted by the theoretical approach, are similar to those obtained in [9] for sandwich panels (thickness $t = 13$ mm), made of aluminium honeycomb core (density $\rho = 84 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and cell size $d = 6$ mm) and glass fibre reinforced/epoxy skins: $n = 1.2$ and $K_i = 2E6 \text{ Nm}^{-1.2}$.

Fig. 16 shows the percentage partition of the incident energy at different impact velocities.

In the graphs, the dot line corresponds to the mean values of each percentage energy and the uncertainty band (at about 68% confidence level) is also indicated. From the graph, it is evident that the contact energy accounts for about the 70 % of the energy absorbed by the panel. The high amount of contact energy can be explained also by the boundary conditions during the impact tests: the *GFR-AHS* specimens were fully clamped around their edges by a cylindrical support-ring with an inner diameter of 40 mm.

4 Conclusions

The study presented in this paper is part of a larger project aimed at the introduction of lightweight structures, made of *GFR-AHS* sandwiches, in the transportation industry (automotive, aerospace, shipbuilding industry).

The mechanical behaviour under bending and impact loading of *AHS* panels reinforced by *GFRP* outer skins was investigated and a comparison with the *AHS* panels (without *GFRP* skins) was done.

The impact response of the *GFR-AHS* panels has been investigated by experimental tests and analytical approach, based on the energy balance model. The model parameters, that described the dynamic contact of the panels, were obtained from the tomographic analysis of the impacted specimens and not from the results of static tests, as it is usually done in literature.

The energy balance model gave good predictions compared with data reported in literature, even if more work are needed to be done to validate the developed approach.

The experimental tests have demonstrated that the light weight *AHS* panels have good properties of energy dissipation and the amount of energy absorption under bending and impact tests can be highly improved reinforcing them by means of *GFRP* outer skins, which can be designed according to the application of the sandwich.

The future developments of this study consist of the analysis of the failure maps of the *GFR-AHS* sandwiches subjected to bending and low velocity impact tests.

References

- [1] K.B. Shin, J.Y. Lee and S.H. Cho "An experimental study of low-velocity impact responses of sandwich panels for Korean low floor bus". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 84 No. 3, pp 228-240, 2008.
- [2] J. Banhart, C. Schmoll, U. Neumann "Light-weight aluminium foam structures for ships". *Proc. Conf. materials in oceanic environment (Euromat '98)*, Lisbon (Portugal), vol. 1; pp. 55–63, 22–24 July 1998.
- [3] V. Crupi, G. Epasto and E. Guglielmino "Comparison of aluminium sandwiches for light-weight ship structures: honeycomb vs. foam". *Marine Structures*, Vol. 30, pp. 74-96, 2013.
- [4] H. Altenbach "Mechanics of advanced materials for lightweight structures". *Proc IMechE Part C: J Mech Eng Sci*, Vol. 225 No. 11, pp 2481 – 2496, 2011.
- [5] A. Petras and M.P.F. Sutcliffe "Failure mode maps for honeycomb sandwich panels". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 44, No. 4, pp 237-252, 1999.
- [6] G. Belingardi, P. Martella and L. Peroni "Fatigue analysis of honeycomb-composite sandwich beams". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 38, pp 1183-1191, 2007.
- [7] G. Demelio, K. Genovese and C. Pappalettere "An experimental investigation of static and fatigue behaviour of sandwich composite panels joined by fasteners". *Composites: Part B*, Vol. 32 No. 4, pp 299-308, 2001.
- [8] S. Abrate "Impact on composite structures". Cambridge University Press, 2005.
- [9] M.A. Hazizan and W.J. Cantwell "The low velocity impact response of an aluminium honeycomb sandwich structure". *Composites: Part B*, Vol. 34, pp 679-687, 2003.
- [10] C.C. Foo, L.K. Seah, G.B. Chai "A modified energy-balance model to predict low-velocity impact response for sandwich composites". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 93 (5), pp. 1385-1393, 2011.
- [11] B. Castanie, C. Buovet, Y. Aminanda, J.J. Barrau, P. Thevenet "Modelling of low-energy/low-velocity impact on Nomex honeycomb sandwich structures with metallic skins". *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, Vol. 35, pp 620-634, 2008.
- [12] S. Zhu, G.B. Chai "Damage and failure mode maps of composite sandwich panel subjected to quasi-static indentation and low velocity impact". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 101, pp. 204-214, 2013.
- [13] E. Kara, V. Crupi, G. Epasto, E. Guglielmino, H. Aykul, "Low velocity impact response of glass fiber reinforced aluminium foam sandwich", *Proc. of 15th European Conference on Composite Materials (ECCM15)*, pp. 1-8, Venice (Italy), 24-28 June 2012.
- [14] V. Crupi, G. Epasto and E. Guglielmino "Collapse modes in aluminium honeycomb sandwich panels under bending and impact loading". *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, Vol. 43, pp 6-15, 2012.
- [15] V. Crupi, G. Epasto and E. Guglielmino "Low velocity impact strength of sandwich materials". *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials* Vol. 13 No. 4, pp 409–26, 2011.
- [16] C. Meola, G.M. Carlomagno "Impact damage in GFRP: New insights with infrared thermography". *Compos Part A-Appl S* Vol. 41, pp. 1839 – 1847, 2010.
- [17] J. Baumeister, J. Banhart, M. Weber "Aluminium foams for transport industry". *Materials & Design*, Vol. 18, pp. 217-220, 1997.

Fig. 1. Load-deflection curves measured under static three-point bending for GFR-AHS ($d=3$ mm).

Fig. 2. Load-deflection curves measured under static three-point bending for GFR-AHS ($d=6$ mm).

Fig. 3. GFR-AHS panels ($d = 3, 6$ mm) after bending tests at different support span values ($L = 55, 70, 80, 125$ mm).

Fig. 4. Tomograms of the damaged GFR-AHS after the bending tests.

Fig. 5. Impact force – displacement curves measured under impact loading (GFR-AHS $d = 3$ mm).

Fig. 6. Impact force – displacement curves measured under impact loading (*GFR-AHS* $d = 6\text{mm}$).

Fig. 7. *GFR-AHS* panels after impact tests ($d = 3\text{ mm}$).

Fig. 8. *GFR-AHS* panels after impact tests ($d = 6\text{ mm}$).

Fig. 9. Tomograms of the damaged *GFR-AHS* after the impact tests.

Fig. 10. Stereomicroscope image (6.3 x) of *GFR-AHS* panel ($d = 6\text{ mm}$) after impact test at $v = 7\text{ m/s}$.

Fig. 11. Temperature trend and some thermograms of the GFR-AHS panels ($d = 3$ and 6 mm) during the impact tests at $v = 7$ m/s.

Fig. 12. Failure mode map for sandwiches subjected to impact loading [12]. The symbol \blacklozenge refers to the investigated GFR-AHS panels.

Fig. 13. Measurements of the displacements w_i and w_b carried out on the CT image.

Fig. 14. Peak load vs. sandwich deflection.

Fig. 15. Contact energy dissipation vs. peak load.

Fig. 16. Energy partition graph.

Table 1. Configuration and properties of the *GFR-AHS* panels.

	Sequence	Number of layers	Material	Fiber Orientation / diameter and thickness of honeycomb cell	density [kg/m ³]	thickness [mm]
Upper skin	1	2	Glass fiber and epoxy resin	[0°/90°/Mat]	1180	1.5
	2	1	AA5754 H32		2730	1
Core	3	1	AA5052	d = 3 mm; t _c = 0.05 mm	130	9
				d = 6 mm; t _c = 0.06 mm	80	
Lower skin	4	1	AA5754 H32		2730	1
	5	2	Glass fiber and epoxy resin	[0°/90°/Mat]	1180	1.5

Table 2. Mechanical and physical properties of the adhesive SikaFlex-265.

Type	Density [kg/m ³]	Shear Modulus [MPa]	Shear Strength [MPa]	Shear Strain [%]
Polyurethane	1200 (Uncured)	0.7	4.5	450

Table 3. Results of the bending tests.

L [mm]	AHS (d = 3 mm)			AHS (d = 6 mm)			GFR-AHS (d = 3 mm)			GFR-AHS (d = 6 mm)		
	F _{max} [N]	E [J]	η [%]	F _{max} [N]	E [J]	η [%]	F _{max} [N]	E [J]	η [%]	F _{max} [N]	E [J]	η [%]
55	4135	40	65	2797	30	72	7438	107	82	4119	49	70
70	3640	38	70	2395	20	55	6700	115	79	3778	28	65
80	3815	44	63	2230	21	53	6263	99	69	3659	60	67
125	3063	37	67	1669	12	40	5194	84	64	3484	33	60

Table 4. Results of the impact tests.

v [m/s]	AHS (d = 3 mm)			AHS (d = 6 mm)			GFR-AHS (d = 3 mm)			GFR-AHS (d = 6 mm)		
	F _C [N]	F _{2P} [N]	E [J]	F _C [N]	F _{2P} [N]	E [J]	F _C [N]	F _{2P} [N]	E [J]	F _C [N]	F _{2P} [N]	E [J]
3	7683	-	32	6239	-	32	3183	11358	32	2076	7644	32
4	9668	7504	56	7862	6321	56	3200	11488	56	6398	8354	56
5	9373	7137	88	7953	6968	88	8755	13212	88	7837	12869	88
6	9648	6660	124	8456	7640	119	9243	13299	127	7205	17911	127
7	10353	7234	131	8514	7248	116	9914	14477	173	7577	16805	173
8	10247	7688	129	8489	7123	114	9397	14246	225	-	-	-
9	-	-	-	-	-	-	10798	14622	285	7842	20316	285
10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7693	21083	300